

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CO-CONSOLIDATED CF/PEEK LAMINATES MANUFACTURED IN STAMP-FORMING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Co-consolidation is considered one effective joining method to allow novel types of integral structures to be manufactured. In this study, carbon fiber reinforced Polyether-Ether-Ketone partially-consolidated tape preforms were co-consolidated with carbon fiber reinforced Polyether-Ether-Ketone laminates in stamp-forming process. Interlaminar bond quality of both joining partners is validated in double cantilever beam test. Results exhibit average interlaminar fracture toughness of 2.54 kJ/m² for stamp-forming specimen which exceeds interlaminar fracture toughness of reference samples manufactured in autoclave being 1.79 kJ/m². Further examinations on specimen morphology and mechanical properties indicate distinct assignments to process characteristic cooling rates, which coincides with studies from literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing of composite parts are dominated by time and cost consuming autoclave curing and manual assembly steps. To tackle this, the use of out-of-autoclave processes and thermoplastic components shall be extended [1–3]. To exploit nature of thermoplastics at most extent and make efficient use of their characteristic features, production of large structures with integrated stiffeners, manufactured in stamp-forming, are aimed to develop. Usage of direct bonding method co-consolidation allows hybridization of stamp-forming process and joining of reinforcements in one step. From a process engineering point of view, direct bonding is achieved by heating the interface and cooling down under pressure. [4–6]

Consolidation in fusion bonding requires polymer-polymer interface healing [7]. Wool and O'Connor [8, 9] described this procedure with five sequential stages, namely surface rearrangement, surface approach, wetting, diffusion, and randomization. The first three stages, until diffusion of molecules begins, is known as intimate contact development and was originally developed by Dara and Loos [10]. Thereby, resin flow causes squeezing of air and resin out of the interface, network deformation takes place, and potential barriers associated with inhomogeneities at the interface disappear [11–13]. The time until full intimate contact is reached can be considered as a function of polymer viscosity, depending on the polymer temperature, initial surface roughness, and the applied pressure. Subsequently, molecules begin to migrate through the interface and entangle with the ones of the counterparty (interdiffusion or autohesion). Strength of the bond increases until full bonding is achieved, which is when the interface cannot be distinguished from the bulk material [14]. Cooling under pressure completes the bonding process, whereas cooling rate is of high influence on both, morphological and mechanical properties of the bonded part [7, 15, 16]. In this present study of stamp-forming, short time to form intimate contact as well as high cooling rates predominate, which is why direct bonding, assuming polymer healing and consolidation, is challenging.

Previous research has revealed dependencies between cooling rate on matrix morphology, fiber/matrix interaction and interface structure [17–20]. Gao and Kim [18], Lustiger et. al. [21] and Khanh et al. [20] relate high cooling rates to low crystallinity and high toughness due to enhanced matrix ductility. Gao and Kim did measurements on G_{IC} to determine interlaminar fracture toughness in double cantilever beam (DCB) test and specified values of 2.6 kJ/m² for a cooling rate of 80 K/min respectively 1.8 kJ/m² for a cooling rate of 1 K/min [22]. Thereby, the two crucial properties matrix ductility and fiber-matrix interface bond strength are opposed to the cooling rate. Ductility increases and fiber-matrix interface bond strength decreases with higher cooling rates, which ultimately has the

effect of composite toughness increase.

In this present study, direct bonding of CF/PEEK organo sheets and CF/PEEK tape preforms is examined. Contrary to existing studies of direct bonding in stamp-forming process, joining surfaces are brought into the molten state separately, providing short time intimate contact development in combination with high cooling rates. Organo sheets are placed in a countersink tool to achieve accurate positioning, heated in-situ via IR and co-consolidated with a partially consolidated tape-preform by stamp-forming. The strength of the joint is validated in DCB-test by determining interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} . Autoclave curing of the same specimen composition was used as the benchmark process. Hereby, direct bonding is achieved under long time intimate contact development, offering sufficient time to create a fully developed bond.

This procedure is considered one effective method to manufacture integral components in short cycle times by exploiting thermoplastics advantageous characteristic of meltability. The partially consolidated, load path optimized tape-preform may represent a structural part that shall be thermoformed, locally reinforced by an stiffener made of organo sheets that is co-consolidated in stamp-forming.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The material used for both, the partially consolidated tape-preform and the organo sheet, is Solvay's APC-2 polyether ether kethone (PEEK) with an AS4 C-fiber. The fiber volume content according to data sheet is $\varphi = 0.58$. Cured ply thickness is specified to be $t_{cpt} = 0.138$ mm.

The tape preform is manufactured at Fraunhofer-Einrichtung für Gießerei-, Composite- und Verarbeitungstechnik IGCV in automated tape-laying by using a Coriolis Tape-Placement Head that is attached on a six-axis KUKA robot. Eleven layers of unidirectional (UD) $\frac{1}{4}$ in tapes are placed by means of laser heating. Lay-up speed is set to 0.2 m/s, laser power is 2000 W, and compaction force of the roller is 400 N. Detected temperature in the nip-point is 425°C. In-situ consolidation is not an object of interest at this point, since the full consolidation is to take place during stamp-forming process. The organo sheet is processed in autoclave, comprising eleven hand-laid-up tapes. Process data is given in Table 1. As with the tape preform, ply scheme is $[0^\circ]_{11}$ (UD). Individual specimen are cut from a single plate by means of waterjet cutting to a size of 260 mm x 35 mm.

Heat-up rate [°C/min]	5.8
Pressure ramp [bar/min]	0.17
Dwell temperature [°C]	380
Dwell Pressure [bar]	10
Dwell time [s]	1800
Cooling rate [°C/min]	6.2

Table 1: Autoclave processing data

Test setup to manufacture DCB-specimen, comprises a countersink tool equipped with rectangular cut-outs to insert the organo sheets and two IR-radiator panels I and II. A sliding carriage is used to move the tape-preform and IR-panel I precisely. To begin melting process of both joining partners, the sliding carriage moves to its end stop, when IR panel I covers the tape-preform and IR panel II covers the organo sheets (see Figure 1, top). The surface appearance as well as the logged temperature of both laminates were taken as indicators for matrix being melted. The set-temperature was determined in preliminary tests, of 390 °C. The sliding carriage with the tape-preform and IR-radiator panel II moves to its opposite end stop where the tape-preform covers the organo sheets (see Figure 1, bottom). The press is closed in rapid motion and then closed with a force of 80 t in a force-controlled manner. With the tool projected area, a pressure of 6.3 bar results.

As seen in Figure 2, temperature at both thermocouples drops rapidly, when mold is closed. Temperature just before first contact is $\approx 375^\circ\text{C}$. Thermocouple of the organo sheet is then located in the joining zone, between the tape preform and the organo sheet, measuring a temperature drop of 155°C in the first 10 seconds after contact. Tool temperature of 200°C is reached rapidly there. Thermocouple of the tape-preform is outside the mold to detect temperature loss of the unpressed laminate due to thermal radiation to the environment. The demolding process is started after dwell time of 120 s.

Figure 1: Test setup to manufacture DCB specimen; top: clamping frame position during heating of both partners, bottom: clamping frame position during pressing.

Figure 2: Temperature log for both tape-preform and organo sheet during DCB-test specimen manufacturing

Benchmark DCB-specimen were manufactured in autoclave process whereas the joining partners are also on the one hand partially consolidated tape preforms and on the other hand autoclave processed organo sheets. The process data corresponds to that given in

Table 1.

3 CHARACTERIZATION

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness is measured in double cantilever beam (DCB) test to assess adhesion between both laminates on peel loading. Specimen geometry as well as test parameters were chosen in accordance with ISO 15024. 25 DCB-specimen manufactured in stamp-forming and ten specimen manufactured in autoclave with dimensions of 250 mm x 25 mm x 3.1 mm were tested with a ZwickRoell universal testing machine. An initial crack, starting at the end of the release film and exhibiting a minimum length of $a_i = 10$ mm, is induced with a testing speed of 5 mm/min without recording data but observing crack propagation with a stereomicroscope. Tip of the crack is marked on the guideline and specimen is removed from the test rig. After that, specimen is marked with a stroke 60 mm in distance to initial crack, representing final crack length. During phase two of DCB-test, constant crosshead speed of 10 mm/min is chosen until final crack length is reached by propagating crack, while load is recorded as a function of crosshead displacement.

In Differential Scanning Calorimetry, grade of crystallinity is determined since stamp-forming process and autoclave curing exhibit different thermal treatment, which is why different morphological structures were expected. Thereto, samples of approximately 20 mg were heated with a rate of 10 °C/min up to 400 °C. Heat flux flow to a reference sample is detected as a function of temperature.

Three-point-bending tests were performed with the objective to examine mechanical performance in terms of specimen toughness under bending load as evident in DCB-test. In accordance to DIN EN ISO 14125 six coupons of each process stamp-forming and autoclave curing were tested.

4 RESULTS

Applicable to a large proportion of both, autoclave cured specimen and stamp-forming specimen, discontinuous crack growth was evident. In the load-deflection curve, slipping is identifiable as abrupt loss of loading; areas of adhesion reveal continuous decrease of load. Figure 3 shows one representative diagram of continuous and discontinuous crack growth. Fiber eruption and fiber fracture is detectable all over specimen width, indicating excellent adhesion between both joining partners, inferring polymer diffusion throughout the interface.

Figure 3: Representative load-deflection curves of DCB-test specimen exhibiting continuous crack growth (left) and discontinuous crack growth (right)

Five stamp-forming specimen and five autoclave-processed specimen were chosen for evaluation. Values for interlaminar fracture toughness G_{1C} were determined by means of equation (1) according to DIN EN ISO 15024.

$$G_{1C} = \frac{A}{a \cdot w} * 10^6 \quad (1)$$

Test results (see Figure 4) reveal average interlaminar fracture toughness of 2.54 kJ/m² with a nominal standard deviation of 0.18 kJ/m² in case of stamp-forming specimen. Autoclave processed specimen do exhibit an average value of 1.79 kJ/m² and a nominal standard deviation of 0.092 kJ/m². Based on the gathered results on interlaminar fracture toughness measurements in DCB test, it is assumed that this short time of intimate contact is sufficient to form an interlaminar bond and thus polymer healing between both laminates in stamp-forming is assumed.

Figure 4: Interlaminar fracture toughness of autoclave and stamp-forming specimen

G_{1C} values of stamp-forming specimen exceeding G_{1C} values of autoclave consolidation specimen matches previous research. Following this, low cooling rates, as given in autoclave consolidation, are related to low toughness. High cooling rates, as given in stamp-forming process, are linked to high toughness as a result of different morphological structures [18, 19, 22]. In this study, cooling rates of 15 °C/s in case of stamp-forming and 0.1 °C/s in case of autoclave consolidation exist.

Compared to previous research, results of interlaminar fracture toughness of stamp-forming specimen exceed those of Sacchetti [23], who stamp-formed laminate stacks that were heated in an oven in contact, by $\approx 100\%$. This is in contrast to expectations that bond strength is less since time for intimate contact development is shorter. Interlaminar fracture toughnesses of autoclave cured specimen exceed those of Sacchetti by $\approx 40\%$.

Morphological analysis in DSC and mechanical analysis in three-point bending to compare toughness of the bulk material of stamp-forming specimen and autoclave specimen test were conducted to reveal relations between autoclave consolidation characteristic process properties and stamp-forming characteristic process properties and specimen properties that may affect interlaminar fracture toughness.

Differential Scanning-Calorimetry (DSC) analysis was done to measure degree of crystallization since strongly deviating cooling rates at autoclave consolidation are evident and may affect morphological structure. The degree of crystallization X was measured using equation (2). Thereby, ΔH_m is the normalized enthalpy of fusion, representing the absorbed or released energy of the sample during transformation. 130 J/g [24] is the normalized enthalpy of fusion of fully crystalline PEEK and $1-\alpha$ is the weight fraction of matrix of the corresponding specimen. ΔH_m equals the area under the endothermic peak. Average results for six specimen of each process (stamp-forming and autoclave) reveal 28% average crystallinity for stamp-forming specimen and 38% average crystallinity for autoclave-processed specimen. Nominal standard deviations of 3.2% for autoclave processed specimen, 5.7% for stamp-forming specimen, respectively, do reveal high fluctuation, which is why results of DSC-analysis should be considered only qualitatively. This matches previous research relating higher cooling rates to lower degree of crystallization and vice versa.

$$X = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_f(1-\alpha)} \quad (2)$$

Toughness of the bulk material does affect failure behaviour under bending load as evident in DCB-test. Since energy dissipation is supported by fracture formation in the bulk material, high toughness of the bulk material does contribute to G_{IC} in DCB-test. To quantify the difference in bulk material toughness three point bending tests of post-DCB specimen were conducted. In total, 12 post-DCB test specimen, six of each process, were tested in three point bending test. Accordingly, average bending modulus is 91.1 GPa for stamp-forming specimen and 103.6 GPa for autoclave processed specimen. Nominal standard deviations are 4 GPa in case of stamp-forming specimen and 3.2 GPa in case of autoclave processed specimen. Expressed relatively, results are 12% higher flexural modulus and 21% higher failure stress for autoclave processed specimen. Average toughness of the tested specimen was determined by calculating the area between the measured load deflection curve and a fictitious load deflection curve of an ideally elastic specimen, connecting the origin and the last measuring point in the load-deflection diagram. Doing so, average toughness of 33.78 J/m³ in case of stamp-forming specimen and 21.00 J/m³ in case of autoclave processed specimen were determined.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this study, a novel joining method of thermoplastics by means of co-consolidation in stamp-forming processes was investigated. On the basis of this feasibility test, direct bonding by means of co-consolidation of a tape-preform and an organo sheet in stamp-forming was validated by determination of interlaminar fracture toughness. The challenge was to create an interlaminar bond with short time intimate contact to realize polymer healing.

Results of the DCB-test reveal higher interlaminar fracture toughness of stamp-forming specimen than benchmark specimen processed in autoclave. Accordingly, high quality interlaminar bond, i.e. great extent of molecule chain entanglement throughout the interface is assumed. Post-DCB specimen analyzation indicate high strength of bonding, showing bulk material fracture in consequence of crack propagation apart from the joining zone as well as fiber fracture at the interface, meaning strength of bonding exceeds strength of the bulk material. The order of magnitude of the gathered G_{IC} values was confirmed by existing studies on interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/PEEK.

Investigations on morphology and mechanical performance revealed distinct assignments of identified laminate properties to the investigated processes with their characteristic thermal treatment, being high cooling rates in stamp-forming process and low cooling rates during autoclave consolidation. In particular, correlations are high interlaminar fracture toughness in combination with low crystallinity, high toughness, low strength and stiffness in the case of stamp-forming and the opposite for autoclave processed specimen.

In further studies, the dependency between tape-preform pre-consolidation and void content of the obtained laminates will be investigated. The aim is to find out whether it is necessary to start with a fully consolidated tape preform to manufacture co-consolidated laminates at autoclave level in stamp-forming process, whereas consolidation of the tape-preform between one side metal and one side organo sheet is the challenging part.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. R. Offringa, "Thermoplastic composites—rapid processing applications," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 329–336, 1996.
- [2] U. P. Breuer, *Commercial aircraft composite technology*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- [3] J. W. van Ingen, "Thermoplastic Orthogrid Fuselage Shell," *Sampe Journal*, no. 52, pp. 7–15, 2016.
- [4] P. Davies *et al.*, "Joining and repair of a carbon fibre-reinforced thermoplastic," *Composites*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 425–431, 1991.
- [5] Costa, A., P., D., Botelho, E., C., Costa, M., L., Narita, N., E., and Tarpani, J., R., "A review of welding technologies or thermoplastic composites in aerospace applications," *Journal of aerospace technology and management*, 2012.
- [6] N. Amanat, N. L. James, and D. R. McKenzie, "Welding methods for joining thermoplastic polymers for the hermetic enclosure of medical devices," (eng), *Medical engineering & physics*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 690–699, 2010.
- [7] C. Ageorges and L. Ye, *Fusion Bonding of Polymer Composites*. London: Springer, 2002.
- [8] R. P. Wool and K. M. O'Connor, "A theory crack healing in polymers," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 52, no. 10, pp. 5953–5963, 1981.
- [9] R. P. Wool and K. M. O'Connor, "Time dependence of crack healing," *J. Polym. Sci. B Polym. Lett. Ed.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 7–16, 1982.
- [10] A. C. Loos and P. H. Dara, "Processing of Thermoplastic Matrix Composites," in *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, D. O. Thompson and D. E. Chimenti, Eds., Boston, MA: Springer US, 1987, pp. 1257–1265.
- [11] F. Yang and R. Pitchumani, "Fractal Description of Interlaminar Contact Development during Thermoplastic Composites Processing," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 536–546, 2001.
- [12] F. Yang and R. Pitchumani, "Healing of Thermoplastic Polymers at an Interface under Nonisothermal Conditions," *Macromolecules*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 3213–3224, 2002.
- [13] F. Yang and R. Pitchumani, "Interlaminar contact development during thermoplastic fusion bonding," *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 424–438, 2002.
- [14] Y. H. Kim and R. P. Wool, "A theory of healing at a polymer-polymer interface," *Macromolecules*, vol. 16, no. 7, pp. 1115–1120, 1983.
- [15] S. C. Mantell and G. S. Springer, "Manufacturing Process Models for Thermoplastic Composites," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 26, no. 16, pp. 2348–2377, 1992.
- [16] L. Moser, *Experimental analysis and modeling of susceptorless induction welding of high performance thermoplastic polymer composites*. Zugl.: Kaiserslautern, Techn. Univ., Diss., 2012. Kaiserslautern: Inst. für Verbundwerkstoffe, 2012.
- [17] P. Davies *et al.*, "Cooling Rate Effects in Carbon Fiber/PEEK Composites," in *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture (Third Volume)*, T. K. O'Brien, Ed., 100 Barr Harbor Drive, PO Box C700, West Conshohocken, PA 19428-2959: ASTM International, 1991, 70-70-19.

- [18] S. L. Gao and J. K. Kim, "Cooling rate influences in carbon fibre/PEEK composites. Part 1. Crystallinity and interface adhesion," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, no. 31, pp. 517–530, 2000.
- [19] S.-L. Gao and J.-K. Kim, "EFFECT OF COOLING RATE ON INTERPHASE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE/PEEK COMPOSITES," *Journal of the Society of Materials Science, Japan*, vol. 48, no. 9Appendix, pp. 157–162, 1999.
- [20] T. Vu-Khanh and S. Frikha, "Influence of Processing on Morphology, Interface, and Delamination in PEEK/Carbon Composites," *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 84–95, 1999.
- [21] A. Lustiger, F. S. Uralil, and G. M. Newaz, "Processing and structural optimization of PEEK composites," *Polym. Compos.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 65–75, 1990.
- [22] S.-L. Gao and J.-K. Kim, "Cooling rate influences in carbon fibre/PEEK composites. Part II: interlaminar fracture toughness," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 763–774, 2001.
- [23] F. Sacchetti, W. J.B. Groupe, L. L. Warnet, and I. F. Villegas, "Effect of resin-rich bond line thickness and fibre migration on the toughness of unidirectional Carbon/PEEK joints," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 109, pp. 197–206, 2018.
- [24] D. J. Blundell and B. N. Osborn, "The morphology of poly(aryl-ether-ether-ketone)," *Polymer*, no. 24, pp. 953–958, 1983.